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Emerging smart city, transport and energy trends in urban settings: Results of a pan-European foresight exercise with 120 experts

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ABSTRACT

Forecasting future trends constitutes a key process for supporting urban and territorial policy making in general. In this work, we explore how the domains of smart cities, smart transport, and smart energy will evolve until 2030 from a scientific and technological perspective, as a means to inform future policies for urban development in Europe. We started our work with an extensive review of recent and relevant research, covering policy and market reports, scientific journal articles, and other scientific publications. Then, a two-round Delphi survey with 120 field experts was conducted to assess the plausibility of the literature review findings to materialize until 2030. According to our empirical findings, there will be several speedy and structural changes in the three domains: we were able to identify a set of 18 statements that are highly probable to become reality in the next decade, whereas 17 statements were classified as plausible but not highly probable, and three statements raised controversy. This work provides significant added value in supporting territorial policymakers' and stakeholders' decision making under uncertainty, as well as in designing highly relevant research agendas, attuned to contemporary and emerging trends.

1. Introduction

Urbanized areas are now home to more than half the world's population. Projections show that urbanization, combined with overall population growth, will add another billion people to the urban population by 2030 (United Nations, 2019). As a result, these areas face increasing environmental pressures and infrastructure needs, along with growing demands from their residents for a better quality of life at a sustainable cost (McKinsey Global Institute, 2018). This increasing importance of urbanized areas to developmental perspectives has accelerated the need to embed aspects related to urban development as significant elements of a broader territorial development context

(Moghadam-Saman et al., 2020). In this regard, future trends in urban settings, especially regarding smart cities, transport, and energy, should be approached under a territorial development perspective (Angelidou et al., 2017; Panori et al., 2021).

The "smart city" concept became very popular in the early 2010s as an enabler of a more efficient way of managing urban resources and addressing growing sustainability challenges (Angelidou, 2015; Angelidou et al., 2017). Since then, the smart city idea has spurred policy-making processes, indicating the need to address urban challenges more effectively through connected intelligence approaches (Eskelinen, 2017), which have gradually integrated smart transport and smart energy aspects that have been found to be significant for achieving higher

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levels of urban and territorial development (Komninos, 2019). Therefore, the present study argues that scenarios for future urban development should consider smart cities, smart transport, and smart energy systems as interconnected; there is thus a need to further elaborate on the ways in which future technological, spatial, societal and market trends will affect them.

This paper presents the empirical outcomes of a foresight exercise implemented for the RRI2SCALE project,¹ in which we aim to identify emerging territorial trends, drivers, and potential impacts on responsible and inclusive territorial development until 2030, with a particular focus on smart cities, smart transport, and smart energy systems. The foresight exercise was conducted through a pan-European Delphi survey of 120 experts in these domains, as well as Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI). Our main research question focuses on understanding how these domains will evolve until 2030 from a scientific and technological perspective and ascertaining what potential impacts that may have on territorial development. This knowledge is highly relevant for policymakers worldwide as they set urban and regional Research and Innovation (R&I) policy agendas. In parallel, the exercise can serve as a source for identifying critical research areas, including areas of high uncertainty, that will call for further in-depth research in coming years. To the best of our knowledge, no similar exercise has recently been implemented in these domains with the participation of such a high number of experts.

The paper proceeds as follows: Section 2 presents the main outcomes of a literature review initially performed to determine a set of widely anticipated global megatrends. Section 3 focuses on sectoral trends, drivers, and potential impacts on future urban ecosystems until 2030, with particular attention paid to smart cities, smart transport, and smart energy. In the same section, the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic are also investigated and described. Section 4 sets out the methodological approach used to conduct a two-round Delphi survey, while Section 5 articulates the survey findings and highlights key insights. Finally, Section 6 provides a brief overview of the main conclusions, along with limitations and directions for future research, sourcing both quantitative and qualitative knowledge.

2. Megatrends

Megatrends are “large, transformative global forces that define the future by having a far-reaching impact on business, economies, industries, societies and individuals” (Ernst and Young, 2015, p. 1). They are characterized by “a high level of certainty, at least about the direction of change, and in many cases, also good information on the likely rate of change” (Rohrbeck, 2014, p. 67). Understanding megatrends helps to identify the underlying processes that will determine—at least to a certain extent—the course of selected trends. Recent studies have identified a set of 11 significant megatrends that will shape territorial developmental processes through 2030, including aspects involving social, technological, and economic megatrends (Artuso and Guijt, 2020; Ernst and Young, 2018; PricewaterhouseCoopers, 2020; United Nations, 2020). There are additional megatrends related to changing system of values, in particular with

¹ The Research and Innovation (R&I) project of the Horizon 2020 program of the European Commission ‘RRI2SCALE: Responsible Research and Innovation Ecosystems at Regional Scale for Intelligent Cities, Transport and Energy’, funded under Grant Agreement No. 872526, is a three-year-long project that seeks to address exactly these dilemmas. In particular, it seeks to understand and further provide the method and evidence about how Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) can be embedded in territorial (urban and regional) policies in the tech-driven domains of intelligent cities, intelligent transport and intelligent energy production and consumption. The RRI dimension in RRI2SCALE is realized through extensive co-creation with citizens (over 4000 European citizens) of R&I policy agendas for smart cities, smart transport and smart energy in four European regions, namely Vestland (Norway), Overijssel (the Netherlands), Kriti (Greece) and Galicia (Spain).

respect to different generations (for instance such as boomers, X, millennials, Z and Alpha) which play an important role (de Waal and Linthorst, 2020).

Social megatrends refer to demographic shifts, urbanization, migration, and evolving health challenges. The global population is projected to increase from 7.7 billion in 2019 to 8.5 billion in 2030, but this growth will not be equally distributed among countries (United Nations, 2019). Moreover, the average population age worldwide is expected to increase through 2030, mainly due to higher life expectancies and lower fertility rates (Artuso and Guijt, 2020; IPCC, 2022; United Nations, 2020). At the same time, the degree of urbanization will rise globally from 56.2 % in 2020 to 60.4 % in 2030. However, evidence suggests that Europe will experience a slower urbanization rate (0.32 % annually) than Africa and Asia (1.08 % and 1.10 %, respectively). Regarding migration, the rate of international migrants is expected to range between 2 % and 5 % of the total global population by 2030 (OECD, 2016), and the consequences of climate change may stimulate this phenomenon (Kaczan and Orgill-Meyer, 2020). Shifting health challenges is another megatrend that will be triggered by the increased international movement of people and goods, leading to faster transmission of infectious diseases such as COVID-19 across vast distances (Dugarova and Gülasan, 2017). However, over the next two decades, technological advances are expected to improve healthcare systems (Ernst and Young, 2018).

As to technological megatrends, the literature identifies technological innovation and digital transformation, hyperconnectivity, changing labor market conditions, and new educational paradigms as the most essential developments in the years to come. First, the recent pace of technological advancement has been unprecedented and is expected to continue (PricewaterhouseCoopers, 2020). The diffusion of these technological advances into people’s daily lives influences almost every aspect of life, from work, travel, and energy to food production and the environment (European Commission, 2020a; OECD, 2020). Second, hyperconnectivity will increase due to the fact that the share of mobile internet users will increase from 49 % of the global population in 2019 to 61 % in 2025 (Global System for Mobile Communications, 2020), while annual air travelers will have nearly doubled to more than seven billion by 2030 (International Air Transport Association, 2017). Third, due to technological advances like automation and robotization, some new jobs will be created, while others will be eliminated or nearly so (Winston, 2019). This reshaping of work will be complemented by two additional drivers of significant transformations in the labor market: the penetration of “platform work” and the influx of new generations, radically changing the workforce composition by 2025, with millennials taking over its largest division (de Waal and Linthorst, 2020; Government Office for Science and Foresight, 2017). Fourth, a novel education paradigm is expected to emerge as education gradually shifts from obtaining a degree to developing skills, especially soft skills (Government Office for Science and Foresight, 2017). Hence, the importance of non-formal and informal learning gained at work and through social activities, volunteering, and the like, as well as of life-long learning, will grow (Nygren et al., 2019).

Moreover, research investigating economic megatrends highlights the potential of a power shift, as evidence suggests that global economic activity will continue moving from North America and Europe toward Asia (European Commission, 2020b; Guillemette and Turner, 2018). More specifically, empirical projections show that the share of OECD countries’ output will decline from 54 % in 2018 to 43 % in 2060, as valued at 2010 purchasing power parities (Guillemette and Turner, 2018).

Finally, environmental megatrends include aspects related to climate change and resource scarcity. As to the former, global energy-related CO₂ emissions are expected to grow from 35 billion tonnes in 2018 to almost 43 billion in 2050 (US Energy Information Administration, 2019). Consequently, global warming is expected to reach 1.5 °C between 2030 and 2052, with a 2 °C scenario also possible (Masson-

Delmotte et al., 2018). In the latter case, resource scarcity will be driven by increases in both resource consumption and depletion, partially due to the increasing needs of the expanding middle class (Artuso and Guijt, 2020). Moreover, crop yields may be significantly reduced in the long run due to climate change (“*The future of food and agriculture*,” 2017).

3. Sectoral trends

3.1. Smart cities

One of the most frequently cited definitions of a smart city (Albino et al., 2015) is as follows: “a city is smart when investments in human and social capital and traditional (transport) and modern (ICT) communication infrastructure fuel sustainable economic growth and a high quality of life, with a wise management of natural resources, through participatory governance” (Caragliu et al., 2011, p. 70). Given that cities can be approached as integrated systems, traditional infrastructure may include apart from transport additional vertical systems, such as energy, governance and urban structures. “Smartness” then emerges as a set of sustainable interconnections between those fields that take advantage of latest technology, such as ICT, connecting those to the crucial environment that is daily needed for inhabitants in a city. Key drivers, trends, and potential impacts of forthcoming developments in this field largely relate to the growing challenges of cities, including environmental issues, along with supportive policies and initiatives, technological innovation, and privacy, security, safety, and ethical concerns. Smart city initiatives use technology to address these issues, both by providing digital solutions and empowering citizens to connect, exchange knowledge, and innovate (Albino et al., 2015; Angelidou, 2017). At the same time, the role of cities in tackling climate change and eliminating pollution is vital (World Bank, 2020). In this regard cities provide ecosystems, biodiversity, and human communities relevant for the global and regional levels that could decrease vulnerabilities and facilitate capacities to adapt to climate change (IPCC, 2022). Smart infrastructure encourages, among other approaches, more efficient resource consumption by improving buildings’ energy efficiency with sensors and optimizing urban transport through real-time data analysis, favoring the proliferation of smart city initiatives (Radu, 2020; Timeus et al., 2020).

With the growth in such initiatives continuing, researchers have outlined several future trends. First, it appears that a more citizen-centric approach is slowly prevailing; it perceives citizens not only as recipients of but also as drivers and actors in smart initiatives. Policymakers are gradually realizing that smart city strategies should be more citizen- than technology-centric (Joss et al., 2017; Sepasgozar et al., 2019). As a result, smart city initiatives are increasingly focused on citizens’ needs and preferences in an effort to engage diverse stakeholders in solution co-creation and to diffuse the benefits of smart cities throughout society (O’Dell et al., 2019). Second, the smart cities market² is expected to grow and become more concentrated. Evidence suggests that the global smart cities market will grow from \$83.9 billion in 2019 to \$463.9 billion in 2027 (a 24.7 % compound annual growth rate), while the market is becoming progressively concentrated, with leading companies seeking to monopolize the technologies they control (Grand View Research, 2022). Third, policymakers may adopt an entrepreneurial mindset to promote smart city initiatives (Smarter Together, 2019). As cities are constrained by tight budgets, paying for the introduction of smart city projects presents a considerable challenge. One solution might be to plan smart city initiatives as financially and socially viable and sustainable projects to encourage private sector investments (Skowron and Flynn, 2021; Timeus et al., 2020). However, apart from attracting investments, public organizations may benefit

² The smart cities market includes many global players and the key and emerging market players in this sector. The smart city market size is generally measured by the total value of transactions within the sector.

from applying a business-model logic as a decision-making methodology (e.g., estimating the impact of proposed smart city initiatives) and to articulate how they will create and deliver public value (Timeus et al., 2020).

The gradual penetration of smart city strategies, initiatives, and applications may trigger both positive and negative impacts. Several quality-of-life indicators, such as emergency response times, average commute times, and the disease burden, can be improved by 10 %–30 %, while a city’s greenhouse gas emissions can be reduced by 10 %–15 % (McKinsey Global Institute, 2018). Authorities can also valorize intelligent technologies to improve their efficiency. For instance, they can leverage data collection applications to support their decision-making processes (Basukie et al., 2020; Bellini et al., 2022) or improve public procurement (OECD, 2016). Moreover, citizens can engage in open dialogues with policymakers, leading to higher levels of trust (Desouza and Bhagwatwar, 2012). Moreover, smart technologies have a potential to promote social inclusion, as smart infrastructure enables data collection on informal settlements, informal sectors, and marginalized social groups, such as women, the elderly, and people with disabilities. These data can facilitate adopting public policies that specifically address the needs of such groups (United Nations, 2016).

However, the adoption of smart city applications comes with significant privacy, security, safety, and ethical concerns, including these three issues: (i) concern about biased inferences, as some applications, such as crime detection mechanisms, can generate inaccurate characterizations that create or reinforce social stigma and personal harm (Kitchin, 2016); (ii) the risk of technological “lock-in”, as in some cases private companies may attempt to propose technologies that depend solely on their support for maintenance, creating a monopoly-like control of smart technologies within the city (Clever et al., 2018; Onufrey and Bergek, 2021); and (iii) the corporatization of urban governance, referring to the risk that the business model logic may be misinterpreted as a “profit-driven or cost-driven logic,” leading to citizens’ unequal treatment as customers and adopting practices that undermine the government’s social and environmental goals (Timeus et al., 2020).

3.2. Smart transport

Smart transport solutions have been cited as key to creating sustainable future cities worldwide (León-Coca et al., 2014). The existing literature highlights factors affecting the adoption of smart transport solutions, including the climate crisis, business efficiency and citizen focus, technological innovation, and the prevalence of good governance. Over the next few years, the transition toward smart transport will be mainly driven by the need to promote and adopt environmentally sustainable transport solutions (Mora et al., 2020). At the same time, the need to adopt more citizen-centric and economically viable business practices in urban transport is widely acknowledged as a key driver of future trends in smart transport (Fishamn et al., 2020). To this end, smart transport applications will aim to transform “waste” travel time into “bonus” time by allowing people to work during their commutes (Vyas et al., 2019). The transition to smart transport ecosystems is also accelerated by technological breakthroughs, mainly in regard to the Internet of Things (IoT), big data, wireless and sensing technologies, and Global Positioning System (GPS) technologies (Macharis et al., 2017; Sadiku et al., 2017; Tomaszewska and Florea, 2018). Meanwhile, the public sector’s ability to collaborate with private organizations and adopt a framework to address privacy issues could act either as an accelerator or retarder of the implementation of smart transport solutions (Carnis, 2018).

In addition, there is a large list of potential future trends related to smart transport. Improvements in transport infrastructure may increase the connectivity between transport platforms, devices, and networks, which could lead to better commercial vehicle administration, more effective and efficient transit management, and better data management (Nkoro and Vershinin, 2014). In parallel, Intelligent Transport Systems

(ITS) are also gaining popularity alongside multi-modal transport systems like integrated travel planners and inter-connectivity (Skeete, 2018; Tomaszewska and Florea, 2018). The implementation of new technologies like adaptive cruise control, obstacle warning and collision avoidance systems, and lane detection capabilities in vehicles to reduce accident rates and increase mobility safety is another anticipated trend (Kakderi et al., 2021; Nkoro and Vershinin, 2014). By 2024, almost 90 % of new cars sold internationally will have embedded sensing technologies that will allow them to share collectively valuable traffic information (Soriano et al., 2018; United Nations, 2016). Finally, embedding artificial intelligence (AI) in vehicles is expected to gain momentum; by 2025, there will be approximately 14 million semi- or fully autonomous vehicles in the United States (Meola, 2020). Additional future trends related to smart transport include the adoption of micro mobility solutions driven mainly by traffic congestion and the COVID-19 pandemic outbreak (CB Insights, 2020; Koehl, 2020) and transit modes like ride-sharing, bicycle commuting, carsharing, and on-demand ride services (Kozlak, 2020; Liao and Correia, 2020; Viechnicki et al., 2015). The size of the smart transport market will jump from \$94.5 billion to \$156.5 billion between 2020 and 2025 (Markets and Markets, 2020).

The positive and negative impacts of the evolution of smart transport have also been investigated in the literature. More specifically, incorporating autonomous technologies into smart mobility ecosystems will create societal benefits (e.g., reducing road fatalities, lowering fuel consumption, and shortening travel times) that might reach an amount of \$1.3 trillion annually in the United States (Lang et al., 2021). Smart transport policies will also help decrease the amount of time traveling, congestion levels, and CO₂ emissions. From an economic perspective, smart transport systems will increase productivity and macroeconomic efficiency and influence the manufacturing industry, leading to new business models (Mangiaracina et al., 2017). However, ethical issues related to smart transport, such as liability in traffic accidents involving autonomous vehicles and the elimination of human control over vehicles, have already triggered vigorous debates (Bashayreh et al., 2021; Lacinák et al., 2018). Moreover, the increasing integration of IoT devices in smart transport applications will require organizations, authorities, and businesses to handle large volumes of data, even as Information and Communication Technology (ICT) infrastructures will become more complicated and vulnerable (Zahra et al., 2021). This may also increase citizens' reluctance to provide personal data, such as credit card information, with negative market implications (Sadiku et al., 2017).

3.3. Smart energy

The transformation of the energy sector (commonly called the “energy transition”) entails two main aspects: decarbonization and the decentralization of energy systems (Hübner, 2020). Digitalization in the energy sector has become essential to combating climate change since it offers new solutions for decentralized approaches and the use of renewable resources (Zhong et al., 2018). Indicative drivers related to the smart energy transition include new evidence on climate change, favorable regulations, declining renewable energy costs, advances in technology and materials, the emergence of new business and financing models that offset initial investment barriers, and the increased appeal of investments in clean energy, as green power is set to attract around \$11 trillion in total investments by 2050 (Barkenbus, 2020; Deloitte, 2020). On the other hand, the literature also highlights barriers related to the energy transition, including political polarization and protectionism (i.e., the policy of protecting domestic industries against foreign competition), trade conflicts that hamper the exchange of new technologies, increased reluctance among citizens to adopt new technologies, and the rise of the Not-In-My-Backyard (NIMBY) movements (Hübner, 2020; Korotayev et al., 2018).

Future trends covering aspects of smart energy have also been investigated. The evidence suggests that in coming years, fossil fuels are expected to remain the dominant global energy source, covering 74 %–

79 % of the global increase in energy consumption by 2040 (Newell et al., 2019). However, the demand for renewable energy is projected to also increase globally by 2030 (Gielen et al., 2018). It is worth noting that total global energy demand is expected to peak in 2033, growing from 420 exajoules per year (EJ/year) in 2018 to 462 EJ/year, after which it is expected to decline to 446 EJ/year by 2050, due to energy efficiency practices, remote working, and digitized business operations (DNV, 2019; Fukuizumi, 2020). In addition, distributed energy resources will rise as many energy systems worldwide are currently becoming more decentralized, resulting in an increase in the formation of energy communities (European Parliament, 2020; Lang et al., 2021). It is estimated that by 2030, energy communities in the European Union (EU) will own 17 % and 21 % of installed wind and solar capacity, respectively, while by 2050, 83 % of EU households could become prosumers that both generate and consume energy (Caramizaru and Uihlein, 2020). The energy transition will thus mainly involve adapting and repurposing existing organizations and infrastructures rather than replacing them with new ones (Kattirtzi and Winskel, 2020). Moreover, electricity will become the central energy carrier by 2050, with the electricity grid tripling in size (Hübner, 2020). Moreover, technologies such as Demand-Side Response (DSR) measures and energy storage—partly enabled by digitalization—are evolving into crucial trends in the energy sector (Langendahl et al., 2019). Finally, the market related to the smart energy industry is projected to grow from \$52 billion in 2017 to \$64 billion by 2025 (Henze and Thomas, 2017; Kovalenko et al., 2021).

The transition to a smart energy system will have both positive and negative impacts: improvements in citizen welfare, greater efficiency, and more vigorous competition on the one hand, but increased complexity and growing security concerns on the other. Evidence shows that the smart energy transition will result in Gross Domestic Product (GDP) growth, job creation, and human welfare benefits (International Renewable Energy Agency, 2019). By 2030, an additional 1.2 million jobs could be created in the EU if the Paris Agreement is fully implemented (Czako, 2020; Ram et al., 2020). These advances, combined with environmental and health benefits, could improve citizen welfare by 13.5 % by 2050 (International Renewable Energy Agency, 2020). Moreover, better data quality, greater connectivity, and increased automation can make energy grids cheaper and more efficient, leading to a reduction of 1.8 Gigatonnes in CO₂ emissions by 2030 (Giannakaris et al., 2019; Hübner, 2020). However, smart energy systems may also lead to an exponential increase in the number of energy generators, devices, and demand patterns that will require a much more complex management approach (Fukuizumi, 2020). Regulatory frameworks must adapt to facilitate harmonious collaboration between market participants (Technofunc, 2020), while the profitability of established energy players is shifting from the beginning of the electricity value chain (power generation) toward the end (transmission, distribution, and end market or service location) (Bamber et al., 2014). Finally, the extensive use of digital technologies in the energy industry comes with privacy, security, safety, and ethical concerns, particularly regarding cybersecurity (European Commission, 2020a).

3.4. Effects of COVID-19

The COVID-19 pandemic has posed significant challenges to urbanized areas worldwide, squeezing their budgets and changing priorities. According to Gade and Aithal (2021), safety-related hardware and apps, such as medical facilities, IoT infrastructure for contactless transactions and social monitoring, and e-commerce apps have boomed. By contrast, the development of other projects in smart cities, such as smart home and smart office upgrades, smart city LED lighting systems, and smart traffic management projects has been significantly delayed or otherwise impacted, overall leading to a stable increase in active mobility (Kamruzzaman, 2022). In overall, however, it is expected that the pandemic will boost smart city development (Kunzmann, 2020), giving rise to new

urban development and planning concepts favoring chrono urbanism and resilience-driven policy making (Allam et al., 2022).

In the transport sector, COVID-19 altered travel behavior, encouraging travelers to switch from public to private transport modes to reduce the risk of infection (Rodríguez González et al., 2021). In this context, many cities worldwide recognized the need for transportation modes that enable social distancing while preserving the clean-air improvements experienced during lockdowns (Morgan Stanley Capital International, 2020). As a result, smarter mobility policies in cities were accelerated, with the adoption of temporary bicycle lanes and expanded pedestrian spaces. Another potentially permanent behavioral change in urban mobility is a decrease in the number of shopping trips due to the growth in online purchasing behavior during the pandemic (Rahman et al., 2021).

In the energy sector, many solar, wind, and battery projects were paused due to disruptions in the Chinese supply chain. In addition, a global drop in electricity demand tempered the sense of urgency to build new capacity. However, the global lockdowns also illustrated the need for resilience. Thus, distributed storage and renewable resources are expected to be in greater demand in the future because they can be automated more easily than conventional power plants (Morgan Stanley Capital International, 2020). In parallel, the pandemic accelerated public acceptance of smart meters, since consumers perceived them as a safe method to limit contact between them and energy operator employees (Council of European Energy Regulators, 2021).

Overall, the COVID-19 pandemic highlighted trust as crucial to deploying any digital product or service. In this context, policymakers have been called on to address fears of public surveillance and concerns over data security (Heine, 2021). Finally, the pandemic reinforced global inequality, excluding 3.7 billion people who have no Internet access from distance learning and working from home (International Telecommunication Union, 2021).

4. Methods

This section provides a detailed description of the Delphi methodology we followed in our empirical study. The Delphi method begins as an ordinary opinion survey to solicit experts' opinions on a given subject. What differentiates Delphi is that data collection does not stop here. The facilitator collects, consolidates, and returns the collected opinions to each expert. During the second and any later rounds, experts can revise their viewpoints in light of their colleagues' opinions. This method's strength is that respondents can learn from others' views without being unduly influenced by them, either by traditional group communication processes like groupthink (i.e., "the psychological drive for consensus at any cost that suppresses dissent and appraisal of alternatives" (Janis, 1982, p. 1)) or by a few individuals who may talk loudest at meetings or have the most prestige (European Foresight Platform, 2010; Von Briel, 2018).

4.1. Delphi statements formulation

The present study commenced with an extensive literature search on key social, technological, economic, and environmental megatrends (see Section 2), allowing for a better understanding of the broader framework within which our sectoral trends are evolving. An additional literature search was performed to determine potential developments (i.e., drivers, trends, and impacts) in the domains of smart cities, smart transport, and smart energy (see Section 3). The insights gained from these two efforts provided all the information needed to create a set of 38 survey questions known as "Delphi statements" (the full list of statements is available in Appendix A). As far as possible, these statements were concise, precise, unambiguous, devoid of epistemic terminology, inclusive, and unbiased, following the guidelines of Hyman and Sierra (2016). Of the 38 statements, 16 are related to the overall territorial aspects of digitalization, seven focus on smart cities, seven on

smart transport, and eight on smart energy (Fig. 1). Among the 38 statements, 18 constitute projections of potential trends, 12 projections of potential impacts, and eight projections of potential drivers (Fig. 2).

4.2. Delphi questionnaire

The Delphi questionnaire (Appendix A) was structured to allow experts to rate their degree of agreement with each statement and indicate their opinion regarding its potential to happen. To this end, a five-point Likert-type response scale ranging from "Firmly disagree" to "Firmly agree" was used. The questionnaire also provided experts with the option of explaining their answers and providing evidence by means of commenting under each statement. The questionnaire was administered using Welphi (2022), a survey platform specifically designed to conduct Delphi surveys. The Delphi survey was conducted in November and December 2020.

4.3. Identification of experts

A total of 954 experts were invited to participate in the Delphi survey. Of that group, 19 % were identified through the networking approach, 4 % through snowballing (by which existing study subjects recruit future subjects from among their acquaintances), 29 % by bibliometric analysis (the statistical evaluation of published scientific articles and books to identify the most frequently cited experts in each domain, based on the two keyword-based searches detailed in Appendix B), and 48 % from the Smart Specialisation Platform (European Commission and Joint Research Center, 2022). During the first round, 149 experts began the survey, with 120 successfully submitting usable replies (13.5 % response rate). Of these 120 experts, 43 % were identified through the networking approach, 22 % through snowballing, 17 % by bibliometric analysis, and 18 % from the Smart Specialisation Platform (Fig. 3).

4.4. Description of the sample

As to the spatial distribution of our sample, 70 % of our survey experts reported living in an EU country, 10 % resided in another European country, and 20 % did not specify a country of residence (Fig. 4). Participant mix was as follows: 46 % of respondents participated in the survey as academics or members of research societies, 22 % as members of governmental bodies, 9 % as business experts, and 5 % as members of civil society (Fig. 5). In terms of expertise ("Based on your academic and/or professional background, how would you rate your level of expertise in the following fields?"), almost half indicated a high level of expertise in the territorial aspects of digitalization (53 experts, 44.17 %). Similarly, 49 experts (40.83 %) self-reported as experts in RRI, 40 as experts (33.33 %) in smart cities, 32 as experts (26.67 %) in smart transport, and 20 as experts (16.67 %) in smart energy (Fig. 6).

Fig. 1. Overview of the Delphi statements by domain of focus (authors).

Fig. 2. Overview of the Delphi statements by type of projection (authors).

Fig. 3. Engagement method used for the RRI2SCALE Delphi survey experts (authors).

4.5. First round

The first round of the Delphi survey was conducted between the 4th and 22nd of November 2020. Afterward, the results were analyzed to check for consensus among experts. Following the paradigm of [Dajani et al. \(1979\)](#), the level of agreement between experts was categorized based on the following decision rule:

- **Majority agreement** occurred when at least 70 % of the respondents rated either 4 or 5 (Agree and Firmly agree, respectively) or 1 or 2 (Disagree and Firmly disagree, respectively).
- **Majority disagreement** occurred when responses showed a large spread across the five-point response scale and could not be brought into consonance. In other words, although there was a preference for an opinion, majority agreement did not occur (<70 %).
- **Bipolarity** occurred when respondents were equally divided over an issue, thus providing two conflicting forecasts.

At the end of the first round, majority agreement occurred in 16 statements, majority disagreement occurred in 18 statements, and bipolarity occurred in 4 statements.

Fig. 4. Delphi survey experts by country of residence (authors).

4.6. Second round

The second-round questionnaire included only 22 statements. As is common in Delphi surveys, the 16 statements on topics where majority agreement already existed were omitted to minimize survey fatigue ([McMillan et al., 2016](#)). Moreover, the new questionnaire included information on the average values of the experts' answers from the first round. In the end, 88 complete replies were received, which corresponds to a 73 % response rate for that round. Majority agreement occurred in two statements, while bipolarity occurred in three. A detailed presentation of the Delphi survey outcomes is given in [Section 5](#).

4.7. Data handling

We performed the Delphi survey with due consideration of all provisions of the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). After reading the consent form and privacy policy, survey respondents provided us with consent to handle their personal data. At that time, they were given a data subject request form to support any future data requests. After the survey was complete, we took all steps required to make the collected and generated data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR). First, we undertook the necessary anonymization

Fig. 5. Demographic characteristics of the RRI2SCALE Delphi survey experts by type of stakeholder (authors).

Fig. 6. Demographic characteristics of the RRI2SCALE Delphi survey experts by expertise by field (authors).

procedures to adjust the data so that subjects would no longer be identifiable. Then, the data were uploaded to Zenodo (Angelidou and Politis, 2021), which automatically links to OpenAIRE.³ Finally, data findability was fostered by including the metadata.

5. Results

Below, we present the main findings of our Delphi survey analysis. Table 1 provides an overview of our findings in terms of drivers, trends, and impacts of the key focus areas: smart cities, smart transport, and smart energy. Also, qualitative information was sourced in the form of comments, some of which are presented in Sections 5.1, 5.2 and 5.3. We elaborate on those statements and the qualitative information according to the level of agreement between the Delphi survey experts.

5.1. Highly probable statements

Based on level of agreement, we identified a set of highly probable statements relating to key drivers for European territories to pursue smart city, transport, and energy projects in the next decade (Fig. 7). These drivers refer to the need to address growing urban challenges, such as increasing housing prices, traffic congestion, poor air quality, and urban flooding (D1, Table 2), to respond to territorial phenomena that jeopardize environmental, social, and economic sustainability, like urban sprawl, over-urbanization, and uncontrolled urban development (D2, Table 3), and to analyze energy demand and adjust how much power is drawn and from where across distributed grids (D3).

Moreover, it is widely believed that national and EU policymakers are increasingly aware of the benefits that urban areas can extract from smart city approaches. Those officials are thus expected to further support the design and implementation of local smart city initiatives through relevant policies and funding schemes (D4). At the same time, local governments across Europe are expected to actively promote smart city applications and services to their citizens by building citizen skills and increasing awareness (D5). Finally, technological advances in areas such as AI and the IoT will improve the efficiency of smart city projects, boosting their wider adoption (D6).

Moving on to trends according to survey outcomes, it appears that, by 2030, most local governments in Europe will digitize all their public services by embedding user-centric principles such as websites that are simple to read and easy to understand (T1, Table 4). Public transport authorities and operators in Europe will increasingly use smart technologies to develop more cost-effective solutions for delivering public transport services (T2). In addition, European regulatory frameworks will adapt to regulate related privacy, security, safety, and ethical issues; at the same time, however, EU members' national regulatory frameworks will adapt at an unequal pace (T3). In any case, the emergence of ethical concerns associated with smart technologies is expected to drive changes in the smart city solutions market (T4).

When it comes to financing smart city projects, many European cities are expected to encourage investment from the private sector and to adopt more financially viable and sustainable business models for their projects (T5). At the same time, the number of energy prosumers in Europe will increase significantly by 2030 (T6). Finally, it is expected that the proliferation of digital technologies (in all three domains of focus) will not be homogeneous across all cities in Europe. Given their lesser resources, small and medium-sized cities will resort to replicating smart city solutions that have been designed and deployed in larger cities (T7, Table 5).

Regarding the impact of digitalization on territorial development, establishing two-way online communication channels, such as social media or interactive mobile apps, will improve the relationship between

Table 1

Overview of the findings of the RRI2SCALE Delphi survey (authors).

	Result	Share
<i>Driver</i>		
(D1) Growing urban challenges (e.g. increasing housing prices, traffic congestion, poor air quality, and urban flooding)	Majority agreement	89 %
(D2) Territorial phenomena that jeopardize sustainability (e.g., urban sprawl, overurbanization and uncontrolled urban development)	Majority agreement	77 %
(D3) Need for more accurate energy demand response	Majority agreement	76 %
(D4) European and national policies and funding schemes	Majority agreement	82 %
(D5) Cities will enhance uptake of smart city solutions by building citizen skills and increasing awareness	Majority agreement	73 %
(D6) Technological advances in AI and IoT improve the efficiency of smart city projects, making them more attractive to European cities	Majority agreement	85 %
(D7) Privacy, security, safety, and ethical concerns slow down the uptake of smart city initiatives	Bipolarity	45 %
(D8) Safety concerns from the public limit the proliferation of autonomous vehicles	Majority disagreement	45 %
<i>Trend</i>		
(T1) User – centric digitalization of public services	Majority agreement	75 %
(T2) Intelligent technologies make public transport more cost-effective	Majority agreement	78 %
(T3) EU regulatory frameworks addressing privacy, security, safety, and ethical issues will adapt	Majority agreement	78 %
(T4) Market solutions address ethical concerns	Majority agreement	76 %
(T5) Sustainable business models for smart city projects with the participation of the private sector	Majority agreement	83 %
(T6) Increase in the number of energy prosumers	Majority agreement	82 %
(T7) Small and medium-sized cities replicate smart city solutions from larger cities	Majority agreement	74 %
(T8) Only some cities manage to use data for substantial improvements in policy and decision making (i.e. make meaning out of the data)	Bipolarity	43 %
(T9) Citizen involvement in co-design and co-implementation of activities in their city	Majority disagreement	58 %
(T10) Citizen-centric urban innovation strategies	Majority disagreement	63 %
(T11) Entrepreneurial mindset adopted by policymakers (e.g. smart procurement)	Majority disagreement	55 %
(T12) Outsourcing of smart city services undermines social and environmental goals	Majority disagreement	52 %
(T13) Development of new smart public services can be afforded only by wealthier cities	Majority disagreement	63 %
(T14) Central, Eastern, and South-Eastern European countries fall behind Western European countries	Majority disagreement	40 %
(T15) Increase in the number of energy communities	Majority disagreement	65 %
(T16) Fossil fuels continue to be used as a backup energy supply to renewables	Majority disagreement	65 %
(T17) Adaptation and repurposing of existing energy infrastructures instead of development of new ones	Majority disagreement	60 %
(T18) Small-scale energy generation and storage increases and city authorities become key energy strategists	Majority disagreement	57 %
<i>Impacts</i>		
(I1) Strengthened relationship between governments and citizens through digitally enabled two-way communication	Majority agreement	72 %
(I2) Smart city initiatives address the needs of vulnerable groups by design, supporting social inclusion	Majority agreement	81 %
(I3) Shared mobility solutions (e.g., ridesharing, carsharing and bike-sharing) increase due to digitalization	Majority agreement	78 %
(I4) Micro mobility (e.g. bicycles, scooters, electric skateboards) increases due to digitalization	Majority agreement	77 %

(continued on next page)

³ An infrastructure for managing research outputs funded by European Commission programs available at <https://www.openaire.eu/>.

Table 1 (continued)

	Result	Share
(I5) Transformation of “waste” travel time into “bonus” time in public transport	Majority agreement	74 %
(I6) Decreased energy consumption due to remote work and digitalization of operations	Bipolarity	32 %
(I7) Automation and development of the gig economy have a negative net impact on employment	Majority disagreement	30 %
(I8) Socio-spatial segregation (e.g. gentrification and population displacement)	Majority disagreement	59 %
(I9) High market concentration and technology lock-in of urban administrations	Majority disagreement	28 %
(I10) On-demand public transport, improved by digital means, enhances connectivity between urban and rural areas	Majority disagreement	69 %
(I11) Intelligent transport solutions sharpen regional inequalities	Majority disagreement	65 %
(I12) Decrease in electricity costs due to smart energy solutions	Majority disagreement	34 %

local governments in Europe and the citizens they serve (I1). Moreover, smart city initiatives will be designed in ways that consider the needs of vulnerable groups, such as the elderly and people with disabilities, contributing to social inclusion (I2). Beyond these advances, our findings suggest that the expansion of seamless connectivity and interoperability in digital services will further promote shared mobility

solutions such as ridesharing, carsharing, and bike-sharing (I3) and micro mobility solutions like bicycles, scooters, and electric skateboards (I4). Digital technologies will transform travel on public means of transport (e.g., buses, trains) from “waste” travel time into “bonus” time (I5, Table 6). For instance, thanks to high-speed and seamless wireless connectivity, commuters will have the opportunity to work during their commutes.

Table 2

Expert’s comment on growing urban challenges (Delphi survey experts).

“Perhaps more significant for the sustainability of European cities could be other territorial grafting dynamics such as the increasing vulnerability of the natural ecosystems around which cities are built due to global warming.” - Expert 16840

Table 3

Expert’s comment on growing urban challenges (Delphi survey experts).

“[Territorial phenomena that jeopardise environmental, social and economic sustainability] may be a problem for some countries, mainly the southern ones, but it is not a [major] problem for the central and northern European countries.” - Expert 17917

Drivers	Need for more accurate energy demand response		
	Technological advances in AI and IoT improve the efficiency of smart city projects, making them more attractive to European cities		
Trends	EU regulatory frameworks addressing privacy, security, safety, and ethical issues will adapt		
	Increase in the number of energy prosumers		
	Small and medium-sized cities replicate smart city solutions from larger cities		
Impacts	Shared mobility solutions (e.g., ridesharing, carsharing and bike-sharing) increase due to digitalisation		
	Transformation of “waste” travel time to “bonus” time in public transport		

Fig. 7. Highly probable statements, i.e., statements in which a majority agreement was reached (authors).

Table 4

Expert’s comment on user centricity of digitized public services (Delphi survey experts).

“Local policy makers but also ICT businesses have already started to realize the usefulness of human-centric applications for serving the more effective utilization of these applications and the higher performance of resources spent.” - Expert 16430

Table 5

Expert’s comment on user centricity of digitized public services (Delphi survey experts).

“In most of the cases [...] only a few small and medium-sized cities will be able to follow a different way than the one of the follower.” - Expert 16430
 “There will be a lot more sharing and support between cities which is beneficial.” - Expert 17360

Table 6

Expert’s comment on user centricity of digitized public services (Delphi survey experts).

“[Working while traveling] has been true already for quite some time at least in Finland. Possibility to use wireless connection from trains, busses and cars enable working during the travel.” - Expert 16911

5.2. Less probable statements

In the frame of the Delphi survey, majority disagreement occurred in 17 statements (Fig. 8). In these cases, the number of respondents who assessed the probability of realization with a 4 (“Agree”) or 5 (“Firmly agree”) did not reach the 70 % threshold. Thus, these statements can be considered plausible but not highly probable in a 10-year window. In terms of drivers, the less probable statements include only safety

concerns that will limit the proliferation of autonomous vehicles (D8). However, when it comes to future trends, a significant number of statements resulted in majority disagreement. Experts did not manage to agree on whether:

- citizens will be motivated to co-design and co-implement smart city solutions (T9)-characteristic contrasting comments are presented in Table 7,
- local policymakers will design innovation strategies that are more citizen-centric than technology-driven (T10),
- local policymakers will adopt an entrepreneurial mindset in designing smart city programs (T11),
- outsourcing smart city services and adopting business-like practices by local administrations will undermine the importance of social and environmental benefits in favor of economic benefits and efficiency gains (T12),
- the gap in adopting smart city solutions between Western European countries and their Central, Eastern, and South-Eastern European counterparts will become even more pronounced (T14),

Table 7

Contrasting comments on whether citizens will be motivated to co-design smart city solutions (Delphi survey experts).

“[Co-design and co-implementation of smart solutions] will be possible and is happening, but is also difficult given increasing distrust in social media and information overload.” - Expert 17360
 “Just a minority care and are able to do [co-design and co-implement intelligent city solutions]. This kind of engagement is limited to a minority [of] skilled, educated and wealthy enough to understand what is at stake and able to participate in the process. Most citizens are passive adopters.” - Expert 17304
 “Although I agree with the concept of co-design I wonder if the structures are strong enough to actually deliver the concept, and not just a facade of co-design” - Expert 17351

Drivers	Safety concerns from the public limit the proliferation of autonomous vehicles					
Trends		Entrepreneurial mindsets by policymakers (e.g. smart procurement)				
		Central, Eastern and South-Eastern Europe fall behind Western European countries				
		Adaptation and repurposing of existing energy infrastructures instead of de-velopment of new ones				
		Small-scale energy generation and storage increases and city authorities become key energy strategists.				
Impacts		High market concentration and technology lock-in of urban administrations				
		Decrease in electricity costs due to smart energy solutions				

Fig. 8. Less probable statements i.e., statements in which the Delphi survey concluded in a Majority disagreement (authors).

- the number of energy communities will significantly increase (T15)
- characteristic contrasting comments are presented in Table 8,
- fossil fuels will remain the main source of energy system flexibility (T16).

Some experts held the opinion that energy transition requires rescaling or even disrupting system operation and ownership (T18), while others believed that energy transition would be pursued mainly by adapting and repurposing existing organizations and infrastructures rather than replacing them with new ones (T17).

In terms of the potential impacts of digitalization, the survey did not identify any commonly acceptable statements regarding the negative effects of digital technologies on employment (I7, Table 9), socio-spatial segregation (I8), and the expected social consequences of concentration in the technology vendor market (I9). In addition, experts disagreed on whether the adoption of smart transport solutions will improve the connectivity between urban and rural areas across Europe (I10) and whether they will sharpen regional inequalities (I11). Finally, the future trajectory of the cost of electricity for households and businesses remained undetermined (I12).

5.3. Controversial statements

Among the 38 statements assessed in our Delphi survey, three appeared to be quite controversial, with the experts divided over their probability of realization (Fig. 9).

The first statement refers to the significance of privacy, security, safety, and ethical concerns in the installation and widespread use of intelligent technologies (D7). Nearly half (45 %) of respondents believed that these concerns would increase the reluctance of citizens to adopt new technologies, slowing down the uptake and proliferation of smart city initiatives. By contrast, other experts (26 %) were more optimistic, assuming that people (especially young people) would increasingly trust technology.

A second controversial statement is the degree to which local governments in Europe will valorize intelligent technologies to improve public sector efficiency (e.g., to facilitate and support decision-making processes, optimize internal processes, and eliminate bureaucracy) (T8). Although many experts were optimistic, others believed that simply digitizing existing services offers minimum potential, suggesting instead that governments must move beyond simply digitizing public services to restructuring them.

Finally, experts debated the future trajectory of energy consumption (I6, Table 10). More specifically, 32 % claimed that energy consumption would fall in the upcoming decade, due to remote working and digitized business operations, supported by sustained energy conservation measures. By contrast, 41 % disagreed, questioning the previously mentioned linkage between remote working and energy consumption.

6. Discussion

The present study's findings can be used as tools to help researchers and authorities working on urban and territorial development aspects to better manage uncertainty and facilitate decision making at the policy

Table 8

Contrasting comments on the potential increase in the number of energy communities (Delphi survey experts).

-
- "Solar is growing strongly and projected to grow even more strongly; this lends itself well to energy communities forming."* - Expert 16747
- "Energy communities have inherent challenges in scaling up, such as the lack of appropriate organizational frameworks, leadership, and funding."* - Expert 16346
- "Market mechanisms are not driven by democratic forces, and even admitting a democratization in "collective energy actions", this will show, sooner or later, the fact that democracy's underlying principles are always balanced with others (like competence, efficiency, etc.)"* - Expert 17301
-

Table 9

Contrasting comments on the potential increase in the number of energy communities (Delphi survey experts).

-
- "[Employment] will be the key issue of the future. Inequalities in education access still exist and the gap will further increase even though alternative channel like internet might mitigate this. The jobs created will be for people with technological expertise and those unqualified will remain out of the market."* - Expert 16793
- "Uberisation also creates many unenvisioned jobs. Take a cloud storage cleaner, Lyft scooter chargers, private house analysts, personal big data assistances, professional hobbyists, YouTubers/Influencers, what a world we are facing. Getting rid of the old, dangerous, inhumane professions is a good thing."* - Expert 17636
-

level. In particular, the following are suggested.

Regions and cities that consider digitalization an adequate solution to their challenges should conduct extensive planning exercises aimed at boosting relevant actions and initiatives. This can be achieved by exploiting any opportunities arising from European and national funding schemes and regulations, undertaking actions to build citizens' digital skills and increase awareness, and minimizing any privacy, safety, security, or ethical concerns arising from these projects. In this regard, it is essential to select projects that are aligned to the specificities of each city by considering type and urgency of the challenges, the size of the population, and the local availability of resources. Based on this information, regions and cities must choose between replicating projects already implemented by other regions or designing totally new solutions. Moreover, they should clearly specify the goals and expected outcomes of the proposed projects and solutions. This means that smart city initiatives must be designed and implemented using a citizen-centric approach that ensures the adequate involvement of citizens in each step of the process. In this way, policy design will be able to foster social inclusion, to increase efficiency and employment, to improve the relationship between governments and citizens, and to minimize social segregation.

Taking a critical and forward-looking approach to choosing proper digital technologies for implementing the selected policy actions is another key factor. We have shown that within the next decade, new technological advances are expected to improve the efficiency of smart city, transport, and energy projects, with substantial effects on territorial developmental perspectives. At the same time, the technology vendor market in these domains may become highly concentrated, leading to a reduction in the bargaining power of cities. Therefore, they must choose wisely when committing to technologies, since changing technological systems after adoption is often difficult and costly. Regions and cities should also pay particular attention to wisely adopting available market tools and an entrepreneurial mindset. Attracting private investments, outsourcing digital services, or adopting a business-model logic to develop relevant initiatives may prove beneficial for European cities and regions. However, those approaches should be pursued in ways that do not undermine the importance of social and environmental benefits in favor of economic benefits and efficiency gains. In addition, using existing digital tools to support the decision-making process should become a central aspect of policy design in the years to come. Several regions and cities have already digitized some of their public services and could thus use all existing data and communication channels to elicit useful insights and engage citizens in co-designing processes.

From a smart energy perspective, European R&I ecosystems will have to determine their desired level and speed of change in each decarbonization and decentralization process. Then, according to their level of commitment, they should—or should not—take additional measures to increase the number of energy prosumers and energy communities, decrease energy consumption and energy costs, and install energy storage devices that ensure energy system flexibility. Finally, in the smart transport domain, European regions and cities should carefully examine their state of the art. Given the evolving trends in the sharing economy and micro mobility, they should make strategic decisions on the ways in which they could use intelligent technologies to

Drivers	Privacy, security, safety, and ethical concerns slow down the uptake of smart city initiatives.
Trends	Only some cities manage to use data for substantial improvements in policy and decision making (i.e. make meaning out of the data)
Impacts	Decreased energy consumption due to remote work and digitalization of operations

Fig. 9. Controversial statements i.e., statements in which there was a bipolarity (authors).

Table 10

Contrasting comments on the future of energy consumption (Delphi survey experts).

<p>“Energy consumption will fall in the coming decade - but not necessarily through the indicated developments (which are rather technology-focused). I think of various social-cultural-political-economic developments that will drive away from current consumption patterns.” - Expert 16778</p> <p>“I keep my option. The energy consumption has increased during the last decades and this trend will be same in the future. Each citizen will use more energy to communicate, save data... And cities will also increase their consumption to manage the smart technologies. The statement that smart means less energy is only right if you do not integrate all the products life cycle impact.” - Expert 17836</p> <p>“[...] remote working implies that the worker will still consume energy while working from a remote location. Moreover, the distributed nature of remote working removes the advantages of economies of scale when it comes, for example, to mass public transport or organised working environments.” - Expert 16346</p>

improve the mobility experience of daily commuters, enhance urban-rural connectivity, and minimize inequalities among regions.

7. Conclusions

Given the urgent need to address growing urban challenges (e.g., increasing housing prices, traffic congestion, poor air quality, and urban flooding), pursuing and carefully planning smart city projects in the areas of governance, energy, transport, and health, among others, is an option worth seriously considering, especially now that technological advances in areas such as AI and the IoT can improve the efficiency of smart city projects in these sectors, making them even more attractive to European cities.

Our analysis, based on an extended Delphi survey encompassing 120 experts on the abovementioned fields, has shown that the domains of smart cities, smart transport, and smart energy will undergo a process of speedy and sometimes structural change in the coming years, integrating specific drivers, trends and impacts in each case. The findings suggest that there are several developments that are already well underway or likely to emerge in the next decade. In particular, we identified a set of 18 statements that are highly probable to appear in the next ten years, including trends referring to user – centric digitalization of public services, cost-effectiveness of intelligent technologies in public transport, adaptation of the EU regulatory frameworks addressing privacy, security, safety, and ethical issues, ethical concerns being addressed by market solutions, participation of the private sector in developing sustainable business models for smart city projects and increase in the number of energy prosumers.

At the same time, 17 statements were classified as plausible but not highly probable. Trends referring to these not highly probable statements include aspects of involving citizens in co-design and co-implementation of city activities, developing citizen-centric urban innovation strategies, adopting entrepreneurial mindsets by policymakers, the undermining of social and environmental goals, as well as

the fact that the development of new smart public services can be afforded only by wealthier cities, Central, Eastern and South-Eastern Europe fall behind Western European countries, there is an increase in the number of energy communities, fossil fuels continue to be used as a backup energy supply to renewables, there is an adaptation and repurposing of existing energy infrastructures instead of development of new ones and small-scale energy generation and storage increases and city authorities become key energy strategists.

Finally, the most controversial statements include aspects of privacy, security, safety and ethical concerns slowing down the uptake of smart city initiatives, the fact that only some cities manage to use data for substantial improvements in policy and decision making, and decreased energy consumption due to remote work and digitalization of operations.

In this context, we foresee that Europe’s territorial R&I ecosystems (regions, cities, and towns) will be called on to adapt to these inevitable changes/trends by modifying their internal structures and processes to make faster and more efficient decisions, transition toward more participatory governance models, nurture fruitful relationships within their innovation ecosystems, and adopt mission-oriented policies to achieve their sustainability goals. Regarding potential practical implications, our work offers three significant contributions. First, as discussed in the (2022b) report, it provides valuable insights toward informing policy makers in conducting efficient planning exercises for boosting actions and initiatives that can act as enabling conditions for accelerating sustainable adaptation in human systems and ecosystems. Secondly, it offers awareness in relation to the potential of digital technologies for helping cities to choose the most proper ones for each urban environment. Third, it provides information on future trends and their applicability referring to carbonization processes, such as energy communities, sharing economy and micro mobility, covering various interconnected urban ecosystems.

In the future, we suggest that research should focus on the trade-offs between boosting economic growth in urbanized areas and advancing other social and environmental objectives. In many cases, these two elements can co-exist peacefully, with only a few temporary trade-offs (such as budget transfers from one activity to another). Over the medium and longer term, measures such as expanding 5G coverage can both boost economic growth and improve citizens’ quality of life. Future research can focus on performing more targeted Delphi exercises covering those fields of study, as well as generational differences. Providing such concrete evidence of benefits to citizens and policymakers could accelerate the initiation of new, more inclusive and more sustainable smart city projects.

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Data availability statement

The full, openly available and detailed research report is available on the CORDIS database entry for the project ‘*RRI2SCALE: Responsible Research and Innovation Ecosystems at Regional Scale for Intelligent Cities, Transport and Energy*’ project (European Commission, Horizon 2020 G.A. No. 872526) (Angelidou et al., 2020). The dataset with the anonymized Delphi survey results is openly available in Zenodo (Angelidou and Politis, 2021).

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Conceptualization, A.M.; methodology, A.M, P.C.; software, P.C. and A.M.; formal analysis, A.M, P.C., P.A., F.K., B.T.; investigation, A.M, P. C.; data curation, P.C.; writing—original draft preparation, A.M, P.C.; writing—review and editing, A.M, P.C., P.A., F.K., B.T.; visualization, P. C., A.M.; supervision, A.M.; project administration, A.M.; funding

Appendix A. Delphi survey questionnaire (1st round)

Page 1 - Information sheet

RRI2SCALE has received funding from the European Union' Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 872526.

Welcome to this Delphi survey!

The survey is conducted in two consecutive rounds. The first one takes place currently through this questionnaire, while the second will be sent to you on 23/11/2020. During the second Delphi round, you will have the opportunity to revise your answers on the same questionnaire in the light of other experts' views.

If you wish, you may sign up to gain early access to the final results of the survey.

The survey takes approximately 20 minutes to complete.

Thank you in advance for sharing with us your insights and thoughts!

Page 2 - Informed consent

Clicking on the “I consent” button indicates that:

- You have read and understood the invitation e-mail sent to you and the purpose of this forward-looking exercise.
- You consent to your personal data being securely stored and retained for 1 year after the completion of the study, before ultimately being deleted by the consortium that collected this data.
- You consent to your personal data being processed by the online survey development software ‘Welphi’ based on the company’s privacy policy.
- You consent to anonymized quotations from your answers to be used in reports, publications, and publicly available outputs (e.g., infographics, etc.) of the study.
- You understand that you are free to withdraw your consent at any time without the need to justify your decision.
- You confirm that you have read and understood all the above and been given adequate time to consider your participation.

I consent

Page 3 - Respondent details

1. Based on your academic and/or professional background, how would you rate your level of expertise in the following fields?

Field	High	Moderate	Low	None
Intelligent cities (e.g., data-driven governance)				
Intelligent energy (e.g., smart grid, energy communities)				
Intelligent transport (e.g., Intelligent Transport Systems)				
Digital technologies and their societal impacts in general				
Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)				

2. You participate in this survey as member of:

- academia or research
- governmental body
- business
- civil society organization
- other (please specify)

3. Which is your country of residence?

[drop-down menu with all the EU-27 countries + “other” option and open box to indicate which “other” country they mean]

4. Are you based in any of the following European Regions?

- Vestland (Norway)
- Overijssel (the Netherlands)
- Kriti (Greece)
- Galicia (Spain)
- None of the above

Page 4 - General questions about intelligence-driven territorial development

Please state the extent to which you agree or disagree with the following statements in a time horizon of 10 years from today.

Statements	Firmly disagree	Disagree	Neutral agree	Firmly agree	Comment
1. The need to address growing urban challenges (e.g. increasing housing prices, traffic congestion, poor air quality, and urban flooding) will be one of the key drivers for European cities to pursue smart city projects (in the areas of governance, energy, transport, health, etc.) in the next decade.					
2. Territorial phenomena that jeopardize environmental, social and economic sustainability (e.g., urban sprawl, overurbanization and uncontrolled urban development) will be the key driver for European cities to pursue smart city projects (in the areas of governance, energy, transport, health, etc.).					
3. Policymakers at both European and national level will support the design and implementation of local smart city initiatives through relevant policies and funding schemes.					
4. The technological advancements that will happen in areas such as the Internet of Things (IoT) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) will improve the efficiency of smart city projects, making the prospect of smart city development even more attractive to European cities.					
5. Local policymakers in Europe will design innovation strategies that are more citizen-centric, rather than technology-driven and hence, they will prioritize initiatives that focus on the needs and preferences of citizens.					
6. Citizens in Europe will be increasingly motivated to co-design and co-implement intelligent city solutions and participate in public discussions about their deployment in their city.					
7. Local policymakers in Europe will adopt an entrepreneurial mindset when designing smart city programs and services (i.e. specify the services’ value proposition, use smart procurement models and attribute importance to sustainability beyond funding).					
8. In their quest to adopt more financially viable and sustainable business models for their smart city projects, many European cities will encourage investment from the private sector.					
9. The outsourcing of smart city services and the adoption of business-like practices by European local administrations will undermine the importance of social and environmental benefits for society, in favor of economic benefits and efficiency gains.					
10. The market of technology vendors in the smart city domain will become highly concentrated by 2030, restricting the bargaining power of European cities and resulting to “technology lock-in” phenomena.					
11. Ethical concerns associated with the use of intelligent technologies (e.g. the “moral values” of self-driving cars) will grow in importance and urgency in Europe and will drive the smart city solutions market.					
12. Privacy, security, safety, and ethical concerns will increase the reluctance of citizens to adopt new technologies, slowing down the uptake and proliferation of intelligent city initiatives.					
13. European regulatory frameworks will adapt to regulate privacy, security, safety, and ethical issues that arise due to the advent of intelligent technologies. Yet, national regulatory frameworks will adapt to these at an unequal pace across all EU-27 countries.					
14. Intelligent city initiatives that will be undertaken in Europe will be designed in ways that consider the needs of vulnerable groups (such as the elderly and people with disabilities) improving the prospect to contribute to social inclusion significantly. Yet, these initiatives will be unequally uptaken across European countries.					
15. Due to the deployment of intelligent city initiatives, socio-spatial segregation within European cities within the next decade will increase. More specifically, quality of life in certain urbanized areas will improve					

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(continued)

Statements	Firmly disagree	Disagree	Neutral agree	Firmly agree	Comment
thanks to new technologies; in sequence, the cost of housing will rise; eventually lower-income populations will be displaced to other parts of the cities (the so-called “gentrification” phenomenon).					
16. Intelligent technologies within the next decade will have a negative net impact on employment in Europe, due to automation and large adoption/promotion of the gig economy (the so-called “uberisation”).					

Page 5 - Intelligent cities

Please state the extent to which you agree or disagree with the following statements in a time horizon of 10 years from today.

Statements	Firmly disagree	Disagree	Neutral agree	Firmly agree	Comment
1. Most local governments in Europe will digitize all their public services, while ensuring that user-centricity principles (e.g., websites that are simple to read and easy to understand, ‘once only principle’, availability through mobile apps) are well embedded in their design.					
2. Only a few local governments in Europe will manage to use intelligent technologies for data collection and analysis in ways that help them improve their efficiency (e.g., improve decision-making processes, optimize internal processes and eliminate bureaucracy).					
3. The establishment of two-way online communication channels (e.g., via social media or interactive mobile apps) will improve the relationship between local governments in Europe and the citizens they serve.					
4. Local governments across Europe will actively promote the use of intelligent city applications/services to their citizens by building citizen skills and increasing awareness.					
5. In the next 10 years, small and medium-sized cities, due to fewer resources, will resort to replicating smart city solutions that have been designed and deployed in larger cities.					
6. Today, cities in Central, Eastern and South-Eastern Europe fall behind their Western European counterparts in the adoption of intelligent city solutions and this gap will become even more pronounced in the next 10 years.					
7. The costs of development and deployment of novel smart public services will continue being higher than the costs of replication of solutions already tested in other cities, and thus novel services will be more affordable for the wealthier EU-27 cities.					

Page 6 - Intelligent transport

Please state the extent to which you agree or disagree with the following statements in a time horizon of 10 years from today.

Statements	Firmly disagree	Disagree	Neutral agree	Firmly agree	Comment
1. Public transport authorities and operators in Europe will mainly use intelligent technologies to develop more cost-effective solutions for the delivery of public transport services.					
2. The number of either semi- or fully autonomous vehicles by 2030 will not increase significantly in Europe, due to public concerns regarding their safety.					
3. Intelligent technologies will be transforming travel via public means of transport (bus, trains) from “waste” travel time to “bonus” time in Europe. For instance, thanks to high-speed and seamless wireless connectivity, commuters will have the opportunity to work during their commuting time.					
4. The expansion of seamless connectivity and interoperability in digital services in European cities will further promote shared mobility solutions (e.g., ridesharing, carsharing and bike-sharing).					
5. The expansion of seamless connectivity and interoperability in digital services in European cities will urge the evolution of micro mobility (e.g. bicycles, scooters, electric skateboards).					
6. The adoption of intelligent transport solutions will sharpen regional inequalities, as advanced regions with the necessary resources (infrastructures, financial capacity, etc.) will outpace the less developed ones.					
7. The use of Big Data and Artificial Intelligence (AI) will significantly contribute in the development and uptake of interconnected on-demand public transport in the next decade at regional level, also improving the connectivity between urban and rural areas across Europe.					

Page 7 - Intelligent energy

Please state the extent to which you agree or disagree with the following statements in a time horizon of 10 years from today.

Statements	Firmly disagree	Disagree	Neutral agree	Firmly agree	Comment
1. The energy system transition will be pursued mainly by adapting and repurposing existing organizations and infrastructures and not replacing them with new ones. To this end, intelligent technologies will be introduced in the energy domain without fundamentally disrupting or rescaling system operation and ownership.					
2. Digitalization and smaller-scale generation and storage will drive a rescaling and decentralization of the system, both technically and institutionally, with regional and city/local authorities becoming key energy strategists.					
3. By 2030 the number of energy prosumers (i.e. individuals that both produce and consume energy) will significantly increase in Europe.					
4. The number of energy communities (i.e. communities that engage in collective energy actions guided by open and democratic participation and governance) will significantly increase in Europe.					
5. The adoption of intelligent energy solutions in Europe will significantly decrease the cost of electricity for households and businesses.					
6. Currently, the existing grid and the existing fossil fuel system are used to back up supply when energy from renewables is not available. This will continue being the norm in the next decade.					
7. Energy consumption can be expected to fall in the coming decade, due to remote working and digitized business operations, supported by sustained energy conservation measures.					
8. The need to analyze demand and adjust how much power is drawn and from where across the distributed grids will drive the advancement of intelligent technologies such as predictive AI, machine learning, IoT and blockchain.					

Appendix B. Searches for the identification of experts by keywords

Two searches were performed in October and November 2020 in the Web of Science with the following combination of keywords. In the first search, we identified 118 experts, while we identified 156 experts in the second.

TOPIC: (“Responsible Research Innovation”) OR TOPIC: (“Responsible Research and Innovation”) OR TOPIC: (“Responsible Research & Innovation”) OR TOPIC: (“Gender Equality” AND “Smart Cities” OR “Intelligent Cities” OR “Smart transport” OR “Intelligent Transport” OR “Smart Energy” OR “Intelligent Energy”) OR TOPIC: (“Open Access” AND “Smart Cities” OR “Intelligent Cities” OR “Smart transport” OR “Intelligent Transport” OR “Smart Energy” OR “Intelligent Energy”) OR TOPIC: (“Ethics” AND “Smart Cities” OR “Intelligent Cities” OR “Smart transport” OR “Intelligent Transport” OR “Smart Energy” OR “Intelligent Energy”) OR TOPIC: (“Public Engagement” AND “Smart Cities” OR “Intelligent Cities” OR “Smart transport” OR “Intelligent Transport” OR “Smart Energy” OR “Intelligent Energy”) OR TOPIC: (“Governance” AND “Smart Cities” OR “Intelligent Cities” OR “Smart transport” OR “Intelligent Transport” OR “Smart Energy” OR “Intelligent Energy”) OR TOPIC: (“Science Education” AND “Smart Cities” OR “Intelligent Cities” OR “Smart transport” OR “Intelligent Transport” OR “Smart Energy” OR “Intelligent Energy”) OR TOPIC: (“Smart Cities” AND “Governance”) OR TOPIC: (“Smart City” AND “Governance”) OR TOPIC: (“Intelligent City” AND “Governance”) OR TOPIC: (“Intelligent Cities” AND “Governance”) OR TOPIC: (“Smart Transport” AND “Governance”) OR TOPIC: (“Intelligent Transport” AND “Governance”) AND “Governance”) OR TOPIC: (“Smart Mobility” AND “Governance”) OR TOPIC: (“Intelligent Mobility” AND “Governance”) OR TOPIC: (“Smart Energy” AND “Governance”) OR TOPIC: (“Intelligent Energy” AND “Governance”) OR TOPIC: (“Smart Grid” AND “Governance”) OR TOPIC: (“Intelligent Grid” AND “Governance”) OR TOPIC: (“Smart Cities” AND “Policy”) OR TOPIC: (“Smart City” AND “Policy”) OR TOPIC: (“Intelligent City” AND “Policy”) OR TOPIC: (“Intelligent Cities” AND “Policy”) OR TOPIC: (“Smart Transport” AND “Policy”) OR TOPIC: (“Intelligent Transport” AND “Policy”) OR TOPIC: (“Smart Mobility” AND “Policy”) OR TOPIC: (“Intelligent Mobility” AND “Policy”) OR TOPIC: (“Smart Energy” AND “Policy”) OR TOPIC: (“Intelligent Energy” AND “Policy”) OR TOPIC: (“Smart Grid” AND “Policy”) OR TOPIC: (“Intelligent Grid” AND “Policy”).

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